

NET-Fuels – Integrating negative emission technologies in biofuels production.

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Abstract

NET-Fuels is a pioneering EU-funded research and innovation project that demonstrates a complete lab-scale process chain for climate-positive fuel production. The system integrates multiple technologies - each of which can also operate independently in diverse contexts - to produce valuable outputs such as bio-oil, hydrogen, synthetic methane, and certified biochar starting with biogenic residues. At the core of NET-Fuels is the modular combination of Thermocatalytic Reforming (TCR®), non-oxidative use of biochar to achieve Biochar Carbon Storage (BCS), and oxyfuel combustion. Fraunhofer UMSICHT is responsible for developing and testing the pyrolysis and oxyfuel subsystems, converting biogenic residues into syngas, stable biochar, and oil. Hydrogen is separated from the syngas via Vacuum Pressure Swing Adsorption (VPSA), while the remaining tail gas is used in oxyfuel combustion to recover energy and capture CO₂ with a purity of 97%. The oxygen required for combustion is supplied by Leitat's Bioelectrochemical Methanation (BEM) system, which simultaneously produces synthetic methane from the captured CO₂ - closing the carbon loop. The TCR®-oil can be upgraded to fully equivalent substitutes for gasoline and diesel—compliant with European standards EN228 and EN590, which has been established in previous research projects. The technical process integration is ongoing; thus, the paper shows preliminary results.

Introduction

The EU-funded NET-Fuels project develops a novel, integrated approach to renewable syngas and hydrogen production, while simultaneously enabling negative emissions through advanced carbon management strategies. By combining biomass pyrolysis (TCR®), non-oxidative use of biochar for biochar carbon storage, and Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage or Utilization (BECCS, BECCU) via oxyfuel combustion, the project addresses both energy transition and climate mitigation goals and aims to take pyrogenic carbon capture and storage (PyCCS[1]) to the next stage. Within this framework, Fraunhofer UMSICHT focuses on the development and optimization of the pyrolysis and oxyfuel subsystems. Biogenic residues are thermochemically converted via Thermocatalytic Reforming (TCR®) into a volatile gas phase, solid biochar and TCR®-oil. The biochar, containing stable carbon compounds, is either sequestered or valorised in long-term applications, leading to certified carbon removal. The volatile fraction is upgraded by thermal treatment within the TCR®-unit to high-quality syngas, from which hydrogen is extracted using Vacuum Pressure Swing Adsorption (VPSA). The remaining tail gas is utilized in the oxyfuel process, ensuring efficient energy recovery and CO₂ capture. The thermally stable oil is used in refineries. A central innovation of NET-Fuels is the integration of oxyfuel combustion to utilize syngas and generate a concentrated CO₂ stream suitable for capture and storage. The oxygen required for this process is provided by Leitat's Bioelectrochemical Methanation (BEM) system, which produces oxygen as a by-

product while converting captured CO₂ into synthetic methane. This coupling not only enhances overall system carbon efficiency but also creates a circular carbon economy by linking carbon capture (biochar) with utilization (synthetic methane). The modular and decentralized design of the NET-Fuels system allows for flexible deployment both in rural and industrial regions. The project thus contributes to the development of regional value chains and supports the implementation of the European Green Deal and hydrogen strategy. This publication will showcase NET-Fuels approach to system integration, process development, and environmental assessment, while highlighting the broader impact of NET-Fuels as a platform technology for a climate-positive energy future. Although full system integration is still underway, preliminary results already highlight the potential of NET-Fuels as a flexible, decentralized platform for regional deployment.

Figure 1: NET-Fuels in a nutshell. TCR® = thermo-catalytic reforming (pyrolysis technology). EBC = European Biochar Certificate [2].

TCR® Process and TCR®-Oil as potential drop-in fuel in refineries

Thermo-Catalytic Reforming (TCR®) is a pyrolysis-based process developed by Fraunhofer UMSICHT to convert waste into biofuels and chemicals. It combines intermediate pyrolysis at moderate temperatures with high-temperature catalytic reforming, producing syngas and organic vapors with enhanced properties.

Figure 2: Illustration of the Thermo-Catalytic Reforming reactor [own illustration]

The intermediate pyrolysis step is operated at 400-500 °C in an auger reactor with a residence

time between 5 and 15 minutes of the solid material. Biomass is converted to biochar and collected in the reforming reactor (moving bed reactor). Finally, the reforming treatment is performed using biochar as a moving bed reactor through which the intermediate pyrolysis vapors flow, thus creating a catalytic effect in all products and improving their physicochemical properties [3, 4]. The temperature of the post reformer is between 500 and 700°C. The higher post reformer temperature forms a higher yield of syngas. The upgraded vapors are then condensed and make three different products, which are a bio-oil fraction (6-12 wt%), an aqueous phase (18-26 wt%), and syngas fraction (19-45 wt%).

The unique selling point of the TCR® approach is the quality of the generated conversion products. The main compounds of syngas are hydrogen (up to 45 vol%) and then carbon dioxide (35 vol% maximum), carbon monoxide (25 vol% maximum), methane and some other hydrocarbons. In the chapters **Gas cleaning** and **Oxyfuel combustion** the further utilization of the syngas is discussed. The biochar from TCR® can conform with the EU fertilizing product regulation (EU 2019/1009, depending on feedstock selection) with the expected requirements for carbon removal certification according to EU 2024/3012. In chapter **Biochar quality and certification** more details about biochar quality and utilization in the context of NET-Fuels is discussed.

Especially the produced **biooil** exhibits certain properties that were previously unknown in this form from the slow to intermediate pyrolysis of biomass. Bio-oils derived from the Thermo-Catalytic Reforming (TCR®) exhibit chemical and physical properties that significantly differ from conventional petroleum-derived crude oils. These differences are primarily associated with higher oxygen contents and high viscosity. Consequently, an upgrading step is crucial to transform raw bio-oils. Among the available upgrading technologies, catalytic hydrotreatment is a well-established method in fossil oil refineries [5]. This process enables the removal of heteroatoms, the stabilization of reactive components, and the conversion of oxygenates into hydrocarbons with fuel-like properties.[6]

The catalytic hydrogenation of bio-oils represents a decisive technological step to achieve specifications comparable to established fuel standards such as EN 228 (gasoline) and EN 590 (diesel). In practice, the hydrotreatment approach has proven its particularly effectiveness. In an initial stabilization stage under moderate conditions, the most reactive oxygenated species are selectively converted, thus suppressing undesirable side reactions such as coking and polymerization. A subsequent deep hydrodeoxygenation stage, typically operated under higher pressures and temperatures, facilitates the comprehensive removal of residual oxygen, nitrogen, and sulfur while simultaneously saturating unsaturated bonds. Experimental investigations with TCR®-derived oils have demonstrated that fractions can be obtained whose distillation profiles and calorific values fall within the specification ranges of conventional gasoline and diesel products. [7]

Figure 3: Visual comparison of raw bio-oil, hydrotreated oil and upgraded fuel fractions

These results underscore the potential of hydrotreated bio-oils not merely as blending components but as genuine drop-in fuels, capable of substituting fossil-derived refinery streams without requiring substantial modifications to the existing infrastructure. [7]

In summary, the upgrading of TCR® oils through catalytic hydrotreatment and distillation provides a robust route to the production of norm-compliant fuels. Consequently, the technology holds strong potential to contribute to the decarbonization of the transportation fuel sector.

Biochar quality & certification

In the context of NET-Fuels, negative emissions are generated by the non-oxidative use of the produced biochar. NET-Fuels focuses on the use of biogenic residues from forestry and agriculture, and in turn the use of biochar is researched in these industries, i.e. as a soil amendment and a carrier material for fertilizers. As a prerequisite of any type of biochar application, product safety and compliance with the application-specific regulations must be ensured. In an additional step, carbon sink certificate (also referred to as carbon removal certificate) can only be granted, if the quality of the biochar fulfils an accepted standard and the non-oxidative use of biochar is confirmed.

Biochar product regulation, quality assurance and certification

A prerequisite for any use of biochar in soil is compliance with the relevant legal framework, whereby there are parallel national and EU regulations. Examples of national regulations include the Fertilizer Ordinance (Düngemittelverordnung) in Germany, which only permits biochar from wood with at least 80% C, or the Danish Ordinance on the use of waste for agricultural purposes (Bekendtgørelse om anvendelse af affald til jordbrugsformål, BEK nr 1001, 27/06/2018) that allows pyrolysis as a treatment for digestate, manure and other defined secondary biomass prior to soil application. At the EU-level, the EU 2019/1009 ordinance allows the use of a broad range of biogenic residues in fertilizing products. On top, the European Biochar Certificate (EBC, REF) [8] is as system for third-party certified quality assurance in biochar production that was established in 2014 and is a generally accepted industry standard for biochar production with distinct certification classes for use in animal feed, soils, and materials. Key aspects of EBC include to sustainable biochar production with regard to feedstock provision and efficient use of energy generated by biochar production as well as the regular sampling [9] and analysis of biochar to provide representative data on elemental composition and pollutant content [10]. NET-Fuels biochars have been produced from digestate, hops extraction residue, vine pruning residues, and forest wood analyzed according to EBC Guidelines (Table 1).

The parameters of the biochar samples are within the expected range for the respective feedstock. Molar ratio of hydrogen to organic carbon is well below 0.4 (<0.7 is the threshold according to EBC and EU 2019/1009, 0.4 is the threshold for highest persistence class in carbon sink certification REF). This demonstrates the stability and the reliability of the TCR® process and enables carbon sink certification.

Of all samples, digestate biochar has the lowest carbon and the highest ash content, as anaerobic digestion has already enriched mineral matter in the feedstock. It also has the highest content of potentially toxic elements (PTE, commonly referred to as “heavy metals”). This aligns with a review paper on manure and digestate biochar, which suggests co-pyrolysis of digestate with other biomass to reduce the biochar's ash content [11]. The exceedances of the limit values for copper and zinc content would currently prevent EBC certification for agricultural use (certification class EBC-Agro). Since these two elements are considered PTE but also represent essential nutrients, NET-Fuels partner ITHKAKA proposes an adjustment of these limit values.

The EU Fertilizer Products Regulation does not specify any PTE limits for biochar as a feedstock for fertilizer production; these only apply to the final product (e.g. biochar-compost mixture, biochar with mineral fertilizers, pure biochar), so that the increased Zn and Cu contents do not per se prevent marketing under EU regulations. Greenhouse trials have already been set up to compare the agronomic impact and to prove nutrient release by biochar (potassium, phosphorous).

Carbon sink certification

The goal of carbon sink certification, also referred to as carbon removal certification aims at precise quantification and third party verification of the amount of atmospheric carbon (CO₂-equivalents) stored in the biochar. Currently, there are several voluntary biochar C-sink standards available (EBC, Global Artisan C-Sink, Verra VM0044, Puro.earth [12, 13, 14,

15) available and operational, suitable for various production scales and markets. At the same time, the European Carbon Removal Certification Framework (CRCF) is approaching operational readiness, with the EU 2024/3012 already being implemented and methodologies for biochar certification expected to be amended soon—paving the way for formal recognition and future issuance of EU-certified biochar carbon units. Therefore, certified removals—including biochar—as of today cannot be used within the ETS for compliance purposes. They can only contribute to Member States' climate objectives or Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs). However, it is likely that CRCF—including biochar will be merged into the EU ETS in the near future. The Commission is mandated to evaluate integration by 2026, and both experts and industry stakeholders are advocating for a phased, well-regulated inclusion of CRCF-certified permanent removals into the ETS.

Biochar C-sink certification works by tracking the biomass (ensuring its sustainability), quantifying the carbon locked in biochar and proxies for its persistence like molar H/C ratio and others [16], data verification through independent auditors, and issuing certificates that can be traded as carbon removal credits.

Regarding biomass, only eligible biomass can be used where no competition with food production or deforestation appears. The emissions related to the whole production chain of the biochar (calculated via LCA) must be compensated with C-sinks prior to issuing the certificate to ensure net carbon removal.

Table 1: Properties of TCR® biochars Quantified following the analytical guidelines of the European Biochar Certificate. Limit values are shown for the EBC-Agro certification class. Limit exceedances are highlighted in yellow.

		Limit values	Digestate	Hops extraction residue	Vine pruning	Calamity wood
Bulk density < 3 mm			734	570	515	574
Water holding capacity (WHC) < 2 mm			15.6	121.3	81.4	68
Ash content (550°C)	Mass%		48	26.4	18.7	1.7
Total carbon	Mass%		47.7	63.5	75.8	92.7
Total inorganic carbon	Mass%		0.3	1	1.2	0.2
Organic carbon	Mass%		47.4	62.5	74.6	92.5
Hydrogen	Mass%		0.9	1.8	1.1	2.4
Total nitrogen	Mass%		1.54	3.81	1.07	0.35
Sulphur (S)	Mass%		0.52	0.35	0.15	< 0.03
Oxygen	Mass%		2.6	8	5.6	3.2
H/Corg ratio (molar)		0.7	0.22	0.34	0.17	0.31
O/C ratio (molar)			0.041	0.095	0.055	0.026
pH in CaCl2			9.6	10.6	10.2	8.3
Salt content	g/kg		14.9	95.8	28.1	0.8
Conductivity at 1.2 t pressure	mS/cm		53	0.02	98	< 0.01
Conductivity at 2 t pressure	mS/cm		68	0.03	120	0.01
Conductivity at 3 t pressure	mS/cm		79	0.03	130	0.01
Conductivity at 4 t pressure	mS/cm		96	0.03	170	0.02
Conductivity at 5 t pressure	mS/cm		110	0.04	190	0.02
Determination from microwave pressure digestion according to DIN 22022-1: 2014-07						
Arsenic (As)	mg/kg		13	4.3	< 0.8	1
Lead (Pb)	mg/kg		120	40	< 2	8
Cadmium (Cd)	mg/kg		1.5	0.4	< 0.2	< 0.2
Copper (Cu)	mg/kg		100	237	173	46
Nickel (Ni)	mg/kg		50	27	5	9
Mercury (Hg)	mg/kg		1	< 0.07	< 0.07	< 0.07
Zinc (Zn)	mg/kg		400	892	112	184
Chromium (Cr)	mg/kg		90	41	8	22
Boron (B)	mg/kg			71	64	48
Manganese (Mn)	mg/kg			903	179	301
Silver (Ag)	mg/kg			< 5	< 5	< 5
Elements from borate digestion of ash at 550°C according to DIN 51729-11: 1998-11 (AS)						
Calcium as CaO	Mass% of ash		13.4	13	22.5	27.7
Iron as Fe2O3	Mass% of ash		5.9	0.2	4.9	1.4
Potassium as K2O	Mass% of ash		9.7	31.9	16.2	14.3
Magnesium as MgO	Mass% of ash		7.4	5.6	6.7	6.3
Sodium as Na2O	Mass% of ash		1.6	0.3	0.9	1.1
Phosphorus as P2O5	Mass% of ash		20.5	10.5	9.7	4.6
Sulfur as SO3	Mass% of ash		1.6	2.7	4.3	1.4
Silicon as SiO2	Mass% of ash		22.3	7.3	22.2	9.8
Organic pollutants in toluene extract according to DIN EN 16181:2019-08 (extraction method 2)						
Total 8 EFSA PAHs excl. BG		1	(n. b.) 1)	< 0.1	< 0.1	< 0.1
Total 16 EPA PAHs excluding BG		6 ±2.4	1.9	0.5	2.9	0.5
Polychlorinated dibenzodioxins/furans (17 PCDD/F) using GC-HRMS						
I-TEQ (NATO/CCMS) inc.LOQ			20	0.865	0.936	0.939
Polychlorinated biphenyls (7 PCB) using GC-HRMS						
Total 6 DIN-PCB incl. BG	µg/kg TS	200	3.75	0.478	0.48	0.499

This confirms that the used TCR® process is suitable to produce clean and certifiable biochar to generate negative emissions via Biochar Carbon Removal.

Gas Cleaning strategy

The Thermo-Catalytic Reforming (TCR®) process is inherently fuel-flexible, allowing for the conversion of a wide range of biomass feedstocks. However, this flexibility introduces complexity: the composition of the input fuel directly influences the syngas quality, including the concentration of valuable components like hydrogen and the presence of undesirable pollutants. Within the NET-Fuels project, the overarching goal is the valorization of hydrogen-rich syngas and the integration of CO₂ capture via oxyfuel combustion. Achieving this requires a robust and adaptable gas cleaning strategy. A central challenge lies in the efficient removal of nitrogen- and sulfur-containing species, particularly ammonia (NH₃) and hydrogen sulfide (H₂S), as well as their precursors. These compounds can impair downstream processes and must be eliminated to meet purity requirements. Furthermore, the cleaned syngas must be

suitable for pressurization and subsequent separation via Vacuum Pressure Swing Adsorption (VPSA). This imposes stringent demands on the gas cleaning system in terms of both performance and integration.

The following chapter describes the gas cleaning strategy.

After the pyrolysis gas production, there is first a coarse treatment of the pyrolysis gas by quenching and subsequent particulate and tar removal by means of electrostatic precipitation, as is standard for coke oven gas [17]

Hydrogen (H_2) is separated from the gas by Vacuum Pressure Swing Adsorption (VPSA) with activated carbon and zeolite layered beds. To obtain the gas quality for storage and then separate H_2 in the VPSA, further gas processing is required to mitigate corrosion and adsorbent poisoning by the reactive species hydrogen sulfide (H_2S) and ammonia (NH_3). Whilst H_2S does not necessarily result in corrosion of carbon steel due to a protective iron sulfide film [18], it will poison the adsorption beds of the VPSA. The quantities of these elements which are present in the feedstock vary, requiring a treatment strategy which allows for large variance in the H_2S and NH_3 concentrations present in the pyrolysis gas stream.

The current state of the art removal using activated carbon is not possible due to the requirement of additional oxygen (O_2) to react with the H_2S and convert it into elemental sulfur [19]. O_2 cannot be added because the pyrolysis process has a large variance in both gas flow and gas composition, excluding the possibility of sufficiently precise O_2 dosage to the gas stream.

The gas treatment of pyrolysis gas first removes pollutants by scrubbing with a biological washing medium designed for biogas treatment [20]. This differs from the closer related treatment of tail gases from refineries and similar processes, where NH_3 and H_2S are most commonly scrubbed with water (H_2O). The sour water would then be stripped with steam (H_2O) or an inert gas after hydrocarbon separation [18]. An unwanted consequence would be the removal of a large proportion of the CO_2 in the pyrolysis gas due to its profuse absorption in the high flow rates associated with water scrubbing. Additionally, the advantage of the biological process used instead is its operation at room temperature and pressure, producing ammonium sulfate salts as a byproduct. Therefore, the novel technological development is the use of the robust biological process to treat pyrolysis gas. The process also ensures chemical H_2S and NH_3 removal in the case of failure of the biological removal.

The washing medium circulates between the counterflow gas scrubber and the bioreactor. On the flow from the bioreactor to the gas scrubber, the medium is constituted of H_2O , solute iron, henceforth referred to as the most soluble ferric species amorphous ferrihydrite ($Fe(OH)_3(aq)$), aqueous sulfuric acid ($H_2SO_4(aq)$), the circulating biology, ammonium sulfate ($(NH_4)_2SO_4(aq)$) salt, minimal quantities of solute air from the aeration process, and other constituents remaining after the regeneration process. The washing medium is acidic, with an acidic pH between 1.5 and 3.

NH_3 binds with $H_2SO_4(aq)$ via chemisorption as with commercial fume scrubbers, directly producing $(NH_4)_2SO_4(aq)$. The scrubber design adapts conventional air purifying technology to clean syngas. The assumptions made in the design are that the process is analogous to removing NH_3 in air with a dilute $H_2SO_4(aq)$ washing solution, which is a gas-film controlled system. This is considered a valid assumption because syngas has a similar density to air. The process design can be further simplified in the case of constantly varying gas composition by assuming the NH_3 quantity in the gas is diluted, giving a constant NH_3 transfer rate. This allows a simplified calculation to be used to estimate the scrubbing efficiency [21]. The reaction is sufficiently prompt that almost complete removal of NH_3 from the gas flow occurs. The other species to be removed from the pyrolysis gas stream, H_2S , becomes solute in the washing medium via diffusion and is subsequently carried in the washing medium to the bioreactor.

In the bioreactor, solute iron, referred to as the most soluble ferric species amorphous ferrihydrite ($Fe(OH)_3(aq)$), binds with dissolved hydrogen sulfate (H_2S) and oxygen (O_2) provided by the aerator in the bioreactor. The subsequent products are iron sulfide (FeS), sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4), and water. The iron sulfide is then converted by the acidophilic bacteria over several steps into $H_2SO_4(aq)$ and amorphous ferrihydrite ($Fe(OH)_3(aq)$), amongst others. This reduces the required dosage of H_2SO_4 , which is subsequently pumped into the gas

scrubber to neutralize NH₃ in a new cycle.

The downstream fixed bed reactors serve three functions; primarily to remove any H₂S in the pyrolysis gas stream when none could be absorbed in the washing medium; secondly to remove the remaining fraction of H₂S which remains after most is absorbed in the washing medium; and thirdly to remove any H₂SO₄ slip from the gas washing medium into the pyrolysis gas stream.

The fixed bed reactors use a simple process, common in the last century to treat biogas. H₂S in the gas stream reacts with iron hydroxide (FeO(OH)), which has a moderate loading and breakthrough time for oxidized iron [22], but is comparatively cheap material, which is economical for single use. Another advantage is the reaction occurs at room temperature and pressure. Heat effects within the pellets do not need to be considered, because the local temperature change when penetrating the porous structure is negligible. The possible sulfur loading without oxygen or alkaline gas is estimated to be 10% weight/weight before regeneration [23]. The loaded material can be oxidized by flooding and aeration, before disposal either as household waste or contemplatable further use as an iron and sulfur source in the bioreactor. Any minute quantities of H₂SO₄ in the gas are absorbed by the binding agent calcium carbonate (CaCO₃), which holds the FeO(OH) pellets in the fixed bed reactors in their stable form. This then forms solid calcium sulfate (CaSO₄), H₂O and CO₂.

The main advantages of the process are that no new chemicals are introduced into the pyrolysis gas, only a minimal proportion of CO₂ is lost, all side products are potentially useful, and all processes occur at ambient conditions in a robust, stable and scalable process.

These cleaning steps will allow the gas to be compressed and to use VPSA to provide H₂.

Carbon Capture with Oxyfuel Combustion

Oxyfuel combustion is a promising approach to apply carbon capture while simultaneously providing process heat at a high temperature level. In this process, pure oxygen is used instead of ambient air to combust the fuel. Due to the absence of atmospheric nitrogen, the flue gas is idealized to consist solely of the combustion products CO₂ and H₂O. Simple separation of the water vapor through condensation leads to a flue gas stream with a very high CO₂ content [24], which can then be captured more efficiently [25] or can be utilized directly. If a biogenic fuel such as pyrolysis gas is utilized in this combustion process to provide thermal energy, and the captured CO₂ is utilized, this process can be classified as Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Utilization (BECCU). NET-Fuels focusses on the combustion of TCR® syngas or rather the tailgas stream with reduced H₂ concentrations after VPSA.

Until now, it has been criticized that the high energy input of 875–1200 kJ/(kg O₂) at the desired purity of 95–99.5 vol. %[26], required to provide the necessary oxygen through air separation significantly reduces the overall efficiency of oxyfuel processes [27, 28]. However, due to the growing global electrolysis capacity for producing green hydrogen [29] and the associated potential for utilizing surplus oxygen, a by-product of electrolysis, the oxyfuel process is increasingly attracting attention in the development of CO₂ capture technologies [30]. In NET-Fuels O₂ is a by-product from the bioelectrochemical methanation (BEM).

Figure 4 illustrates the schematic layout of the pilot plant located at the Fraunhofer UMSICHT technical center in Sulzbach-Rosenberg (Bavaria, Germany), which is organized as follows: The fuel (TCR® gas or biogas) is supplied to a 50 kW burner, where it is introduced into the combustion chamber together with the oxidizer – a mixture of recirculated flue gas and pure oxygen (gas quality 3.5). The combustion reaction occurs there at atmospheric pressure. The flue gas subsequently exits the combustion chamber through the recuperative burner, whereby the oxidizer is preheated. In a first step, the flue gas is cooled in a high-temperature heat exchanger. In the second step, the cooled flue gas is directed into the condenser, where it is sub-cooled to 20 °C to facilitate the separation of a significant portion of the water vapor present in the flue gas. The condensate is discharged via a siphon to prevent ambient air from entering the plant. A part of the dry flue gas (CO₂ > 95 vol.%) is recirculated and oxygen is added upstream of the burner to form the oxidizer. The remaining portion is removed via an

Figure 5: CO₂ content in the flue gas over time measured downstream of the condenser during direct coupling of the Oxyfuel system with a TCR® unit.

Bioelectrochemical methanation

Bioelectrochemical methanation (BEM) is an emerging power-to-gas technology that also serves for carbon capture and utilization (CCU), converting CO₂ to synthetic methane [31]. A BEM cell typically consists of two electrodes, an anode and a cathode, inserted into two adjacent chambers of a bioelectrochemical cell, separated by a cationic exchange membrane (CEM) and connected by an external electrical circuit, through which additional electrical energy is injected, at low voltage. The water splitting reaction at the anode generates oxygen, protons and electrons. Electrons flow through the external electrical circuit to reach the cathode, while protons and other cations migrate through the membrane to maintain the charge balance within the cell [32]. At the cathode, the electromethanogenesis process takes place. The electrode surface is colonized by an electro-active biofilm that catalyses hydrogen (H₂) production. Then, a hydrogenotrophic microbial community uses the produced H₂ to convert an injected flux of CO₂ into synthetic methane [33]. To enable future pilot-scale demonstrations, laboratory-scale studies are still needed to understand fundamental processes, evaluate and optimize electrode and membrane materials, and optimize operational strategies under controlled conditions

This study represents the first coupling of an optimized laboratory-scale BEM with a thermochemical reforming and oxyfuel process chain. The usage of a real combustion gas as carbon feedstock, allows to demonstrate BEM tolerance to gas impurities and variable CO₂ concentration. The next step of the project will involve the operation of a pilot scale BEM plant, with a treatment capacity of 50 L-CO₂ d⁻¹, and its integration with the TCR®/VPSA/Oxy-combustion plant, validating the overall system at TRL 5.

The laboratory-scale BEM system (Figure 1) consisted of three double-chambered cells (100 cm² cross section, 200 mL chamber volume), assembled in a single stack and hydraulically operated in parallel. The cathodes of the three cells consisted of stainless-steel wool (~10 g, 100 cm²), while the anodes were made by titanium mesh coated with IrO₂ mixed metal oxides. Anode and cathode chambers of each cell were separated by a 100 cm² CEM. Each cell operated individually in galvanostatic mode, at a current density of 12 A m⁻² provided by a power supply. At the cathode side, the CO₂-rich gas was injected into the bulk catholyte solution through a porous diffuser. Its flow-rate was regulated by a mass flow controller at 10 mL min⁻¹ to maintain stable dissolved CO₂ levels, ensuring no substrate limitation while preventing excess CO₂ outflow that could reduce synthetic methane quality. The anolyte was

recirculated through a 2 L external buffer tank, where produced oxygen was separated and quantified at atmospheric pressure. The catholyte was recirculated through a 14 L liquid–gas separation column, maintained at 35 °C by a thermostatic bath, at an overpressure of 180–200 mbar and continuously monitored for dissolved CO₂ and synthetic methane production, using online sensors and gas chromatography.

Before testing the BEM system with the real off gas coming from the oxyfuel reactor, pure CO₂ was injected for 27 days, maintaining a dissolved CO₂ concentration in the catholyte of 300 mg L⁻¹, corresponding to ~20% of its theoretical solubility. The real off-gas contained impurities (3% air), with the remainder volume being CO₂.

A summary of the results obtained with the two gases is shown in Table 1. When fed with pure CO₂, the BEM system achieved a higher quality synthetic methane (72 ± 4% CH₄), compared to exhaust gas conditions (61 ± 4% CH₄). The CO₂ concentration in the outlet was slightly lower with pure CO₂ (8 ± 3%) than with exhaust gas (10 ± 8%). Hydrogen accumulation was more pronounced with exhaust gas (18 ± 13% vs. 8 ± 5%), suggesting its reduced consumption by methanogens. This was likely because the presence of oxygen in the detected air could negatively affect BEM performance, as oxygen is highly detrimental to methanogenic microorganisms [34]. Oxygen levels were also higher with exhaust gas (5 ± 4% vs. 3 ± 2%), consistent with the presence of air impurities in the feed.

Table 3: Comparison of BEM performance using pure CO₂ versus oxyfuel exhaust gas.

	CH ₄ (%)	CO ₂ (%)	H ₂ (%)	O ₂ (%)	N ₂ (%)	Carbon conversion efficiency (%)	synthetic methane production (L CH ₄ L _{cat} ⁻¹ day ⁻¹)	Coulombic efficiency (%)
Pure CO ₂	72 ± 4	8 ± 3	8 ± 5	3 ± 2	8 ± 2	71 ± 2	1.14 ± 0.05	69 ± 3
Oxyfuel exhaust gas (with air)	61 ± 4	10 ± 8	18 ± 13	5 ± 4	8 ± 1	58 ± 4	1.01 ± 0.04	62 ± 2

In terms of performance indicators, carbon conversion efficiency decreased from 71 ± 2% with pure CO₂ to 58 ± 4% with exhaust gas. Similarly, both specific synthetic methane production (1.14 ± 0.05 vs. 1.01 ± 0.04 L CH₄ L_{cat}⁻¹ day⁻¹) and Coulombic efficiency (69 ± 3% vs. 62 ± 2%) were negatively affected by the presence of oxygen in the exhaust gas.

The average specific production rates and cathodic Coulombic efficiencies achieved with synthetic CO₂ are within the upper range of values previously reported in the BEM literature, for laboratory-scale operated BEM systems [35]. Remarkably, comparable performances were obtained here using real oxyfuel exhaust gas containing air impurities. Demonstrating stable operation under such realistic conditions is highly relevant, as it validates the applicability of BEM beyond idealized laboratory setups with pure CO₂ and underscores its potential for the future pilot-scale integration.

Figure 6: Laboratory system schematics (only one BEM cell is shown for simplicity) (A); Photograph of the laboratory set-up (B)

Preliminary Assessment of Carbon Negativity

NET-Fuels aims at generating carbon-negative advanced fuels (synthetic methane, green hydrogen and liquid biofuel) with maximum biomass utilization efficiency from a wide range of low-quality and low-cost feedstocks, such as the secondary biomass resources enlisted in Part A of Annex IX of the RED (the Renewable Energy Directive). This includes (a) lignocellulosic residues not requiring drying and pre-treatments and (b) feedstock requiring drying and densification in addition to mechanical pre-treatments. The former group includes nut shells, husks, cobs cleaned of kernels and other fruit shells. Group “b” includes algae, biowaste, straw, animal manure and sewage sludge, bagasse, grape marc, wine lee together with all biomass fraction of wastes and residues from forestry and forest-based industries, other non-food cellulosic material and lignocellulosic material. A wide range of biomass fractions of industrial waste not fit for use in the food or feed chain (including material from retail and wholesale) and the agri-food and fish and aquaculture industry.

In Europe, groups “a” and “b” together range from 200 to 350 million tons (dry weight). The use of this source of secondary biomass avoids land competition with food production and potential threats to biodiversity.

NET-Fuels considers three different selected biogenic residues will be treated:

1. Digestate. Digestate obtained from the anaerobic digestion of manure and maize silage is an important agricultural residual material with great potential.
2. Calamity wood. The effects of climate change on forest stands are becoming apparent in Central Europe. Damage caused by drought, bark beetle infestation and storms has resulted in large quantities of calamity wood accumulating.
3. Pruning. Offcuts from vineyards and orchards regularly accumulate in large quantities, especially in Southern Europe.

The preliminary carbon balance of the process is determined by the carbon removed (captured and stored) and the CO₂-eq emissions due to the external energy (heat and power) needed by the system.

The carbon-negative value of the generated fuels (CR_{Fuels}) is the carbon balance of the process for a reference carbon removal value (CR_{Ref} , expressed in mass unit of CO₂-eq) divided by the energy in the generated fuels (E_{Fuels} , expressed in energy units). A positive value indicates a removal, while a negative one an emission.

$$CR_{Fuels} = \frac{CR_{Ref}}{E_{Fuels}} \quad [1]$$

The data used for the calculations is based on past test results for the feedstocks the TCR® process, and chemical reaction notations for the Bio-Electrochemical Methanation (BEM) process, supplemented by values from literature and estimation calculations. A lignocellulosic feedstock containing 50% water is used. The total carbon removal of the process (CR_{Ref}) is determined by the difference of the carbon nominally stored in the biochar which is fixed to 1000 g of CO₂ (reference value) and the CO₂-eq emissions due to the use of external energy (heat and power) required by the product system to generate the reference value (GHG_0)

$$CR_{Ref} = CR_0 - GHG_0 = 1000 - GHG_0 \quad [2]$$

The following values refer to the processing of calamity wood. To remove 1 kg of CO₂ equivalent from the atmosphere (the reference value), 0.27 kg of carbon must be stored, according to the molar ratio of the molecules. The tested biochar has a carbon content of 76.8%, as a consequence, 0.35 kg of biochar must be generated and stored in a permanent sink. For the following calculations a biomass-to-biochar conversion rate of 28.9% and a water content of 50% of water in the primary feedstock have been considered; the primary feedstock is dried to a water content of around 10% to be processed in the TCR®. This results in a dry

mass of 1.20 kg starting from a total mass of the primary feedstock of 2.20 kg. Based on the preliminary results, the pelletizing process requires a power demand of 0.13 kWh on account of the corresponding reference value. This preliminary assessment uses recovered heat from the oxyfuel process, which covers the drying energy demand. Energy for chipping is not included.

TCR® allows for the production of oil, biochar and syngas, requiring an electric energy demand of 0.04 kWh. Hydrogen is recovered from the TCR®-gas via a VPSA with an efficiency of 85% based on past experimental data, with an electrical demand of 0.42 kWh. The remaining gas is combusted with oxygen in the oxy-combustion unit to generate thermal energy for drying and for the TCR® process. Oxyfuel technology requires approximately 0.40 kg O₂. The oxygen supply is provided by the BEM. BEM represents the most energy intensive process, with an electrical demand of around 5.62 kWh.

If an electricity carbon intensity of 161 g CO₂eq/kWh is assumed, the total emissions of NET-Fuels system would be covered by the biochar carbon removal. The mean EU carbon intensity is around 230 g CO₂eq/kWh¹ and would only allow in the future to produce negative emission fuels through NET-Fuels. Nevertheless, producing carbon negative fuels is already possible today in countries such as Austria, Finland and France. For instance, if we consider the Austrian electricity carbon intensity, which is 103 g CO₂eq/kWh the NET-Fuels process case, would emit:

$$GHG_{productsystem}(E_{Power}) = 640gCO_{2eq} [3]$$

When applying [2] a value higher than ~360 g CO₂-eq of carbon removal, a negative emission is obtained. Taking the reference value into consideration, 0.21 kg of CH₄ is produced corresponding to an output of 2.9 kWh together with 0.49kWh of TCR® oil and approximately 0.33 kWh of H₂, totaling 3.7 kWh, this pool being the (advanced) “Fuels” generated by the product system. This leads to a preliminary value of ~95 g CO₂-eq removed per kWh_{Fuels} (~25 g CO₂-eq /MJ_{Fuels}), i.e. the “carbon intensity” of the advanced fuels is negative.

By 2030, with an EU estimated electricity carbon intensity of 120 g CO₂eq/kWh, the emissions would be about 745 g of CO₂eq, with a negative carbon intensity of the produced biofuels of 255 g CO₂-eq/kWh_{Fuels} (~20 g CO₂eq/MJ).

Depending on the feedstock condition, the heat recovery from the oxy-combustion, the inclusion of the energy for chipping the material, the electricity carbon intensity, the actual amount of carbon permanently stored in a sink and other considerations of the basis of a preliminary Life Cycle Analysis, the NET-Fuels solution would generate synthetic methane and advanced biofuels having a carbon negative value of around 20- gCO₂eq per MJ of produced biofuel from the point of harvest (farm) to energy end use (wheel) when the electricity carbon intensity is around 120 g CO₂eq/kWh.

¹<https://www.eea.europa.eu/ims/greenhouse-gas-emission-intensity-of-1>

Summary and Conclusion

The NET-Fuels project demonstrates a modular and climate-positive process chain for the production of advanced renewable fuels and carbon removal. Central to this system is the Thermo-Catalytic Reforming (TCR®) technology, which converts biogenic residues into three valuable products: biochar, syngas, and bio-oil.

Bio-oil:

TCR®-derived bio-oils exhibit unique properties, including high oxygen content and viscosity, distinguishing them from conventional crude oils. Catalytic hydrotreatment has proven effective in upgrading these oils to meet fuel standards (EN 228, EN 590). Stabilization and deep hydrodeoxygenation stages enable the removal of heteroatoms and the production of drop-in fuels suitable for direct use in existing refinery infrastructure. Experimental results confirm that upgraded TCR® oils can match the distillation profiles and calorific values of fossil-derived fuels.

Biochar: The solid residue from TCR® is a highly stable carbon-rich material. It may serve as a certified carbon sink when used in long-term applications such as soil amendment. Biochar samples from various feedstocks (digestate, pollard willow wood, olive stones, olive pressing residue) have been analyzed for elemental composition and contaminants. The low H/C_{org} ratio and minimal organic pollutants confirm the suitability of TCR® biochar for use in soil. Most samples meet the criteria for certification under frameworks like EBC, with the exception of digestate

Syngas: The volatile fraction from TCR® contains up to 45 vol% hydrogen, along with CO, CO₂, CH₄, and other hydrocarbons. This syngas is cleaned, and VPSA is used to extract hydrogen, while the tail gas is directed to oxyfuel combustion for energy recovery and CO₂ capture. The fuel-flexible nature of TCR® introduces variability in syngas composition, necessitating advanced gas cleaning strategies. A robust combination of cleaning steps to remove NH₃ and H₂S, ensuring compatibility with VPSA and minimizing corrosion and adsorbent poisoning.

Bioelectrochemical Methanation (BEM) and Results

The BEM subsystem plays a dual role in carbon capture and utilization. It converts CO₂ into synthetic methane using biological processes, and provides oxygen as a by-product. Laboratory-scale tests have demonstrated stable operation under both ideal and realistic conditions.

When fed with pure CO₂, the BEM system achieved a CH₄ concentration of 72 ± 4%, Carbon conversion efficiency of 71 ± 2% and a coulombic efficiency of 69 ± 3%. When fed with oxyfuel exhaust gas (containing air impurities) the results were slightly worse.

These results validate the robustness of BEM under real-world conditions and its potential for pilot-scale integration. The presence of oxygen slightly reduces performance, but the system remains effective in converting CO₂ into synthetic methane.

Carbon Negativity and Outlook

Preliminary life cycle assessments indicate that NET-Fuels can produce carbon-negative fuels with a carbon intensity of approximately -20 g CO₂eq/MJ, depending on feedstock, energy sources, and system configuration. The integration of recovered heat, renewable electricity, and certified carbon sinks positions NET-Fuels as a scalable solution for climate mitigation.

In conclusion, NET-Fuels offers a comprehensive and flexible platform for renewable fuel production and carbon removal. Its integration of thermochemical, biological, and electrochemical technologies supports the European Green Deal and hydrogen strategy, paving the way for a sustainable and climate-positive energy future.

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